

Structure of the Degraded *Anacardium occidentale* (Cashew Nut Tree) Gum

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Manuscript received 10 April 1978, revised 3 June 1980, accepted 26 July 1980

The structure of the degraded *Anacardium occidentale* gum has been deduced from the results of methylation, periodate oxidation and Smith degradation experiments. Completely methylated degraded gum upon acid hydrolysis produced 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,4,6-tri-, 2,3,4-tri- and 2,4-di-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galacturonic acid in a molar ratio of 1:2:2:1. This shows the branched chain nature of the degraded gum and its repeating unit consists of a 1→3 linked galactan main chain to which are attached two side chains of galactose and aldobiouronic acid by 1→6 linkages. The results of periodate oxidation and Smith degradation confirm the above structure. The molecular weight determination shows that the repeating unit is repeated seventeen times in the full structure of the degraded *A. occidentale* gum.

It has been reported earlier¹ that the water soluble *Anacardium occidentale* gum is composed of D-galactose, L-arabinose and D-galacturonic acid residues, the two sugars galactose and arabinose being present in a molar proportion of 17:1. Autohydrolysis of the gum generates a degraded gum which on graded hydrolysis gives rise to an aldobiouronic acid, 6-O-(β-D-galactopyranosyl uronic acid)-D-galactose along with galactose. The present communication deals with the structure of the degraded gum which has been arrived at from the results of methylation, periodate oxidation and Smith degradation reactions.

Pure degraded gum has an Eq. Wt. 1327, Mol. Wt. 23250 and D.P. value 17. The IR spectrum of the compound, besides indicating the presence of -OH (3333 cm⁻¹) and COO⁻ (1602 & 1270 cm⁻¹) carries two weak absorption bands at 890 (hump) and 780 cm⁻¹ suggestive of a β-linkage. Complete acid hydrolysis shows that degraded gum is composed of galactose and galacturonic acid in a molar proportion of 7:1. The degraded gum was fully methylated using Haworth's method² followed by Purdie's method³. The product showing absence of -OH band in IR spectrum was hydrolysed and the acidic methyl sugar was separated from neutral ones. The former sugar was identified as 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galacturonic acid as described earlier¹. The neutral methylated sugar mixture was found to contain 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,4,6-tri-, 2,3,4-tri- and 2,4-di-O-methyl-D-galactose in a molar ratio of 1:2:2:2. The mixture was separated on thick filter papers and the individual methyl sugars were identified through their R_G values, rotations and characteristic crystalline derivatives.

In each repeating unit of the degraded gum, there are two non-reducing end groups, one occupied by

D-galactopyranose and the other by D-galacturonic acid units. Two 1→3 linked and two 1→6 linked galactose units are also present in each repeating unit. Of the two 1→6 linked galactose residues, one is a part of aldobiouronic acid and the other serves as a link between 1→3 linked galactan backbone and the aldobiouronic acid side chain. At the branch point, the galactose moiety is linked through C₁, C₃ and C₆ and there are two such residues in a repeating unit. To accommodate all the types of linkages present, the following tentative structure.

(1) has been proposed for the repeating unit of the degraded *A. occidentale* gum.

(1)

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(Galp=D-Galactopyranose and GalpA=D-Galactopyranosyl uronic acid).

In (I), the glycosidic bonds have been assigned β -configuration since the IR spectra of both degraded gum and its permethylated product show absorption bands in the region of $891 \pm 7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be ascribed⁴ to a linkage of β -type. The cross reaction of the gum¹ with anti-Pn-VII serum supports the existence of β -linkages⁵.

Upon oxidation with sodium metaperiodate degraded gum consumed 0.99 moles of oxidant with simultaneous liberation of 0.49 moles of formic acid per anhydrohexose unit. These data are in agreement with the structure (I). Hydrolysis of the periodate oxidised gum liberated galactose residues (4 moles) which had survived oxidation. Finally the polyaldehyde formed as a result of periodate oxidation of the degraded gum was subjected to reduction with sodium borohydride followed by hydrolysis with acid⁶. Paper chromatographic analysis of the hydrolyzate showed the presence of galactose, glycerol and glycolaldehyde. A quantitative estimation revealed that galactose and glycerol were present in a molar proportion of 1:0.98. These results are comparable with the theoretical values expected from the proposed structure (I). Since D.P. of the polysaccharide is 17, the repeating unit occurs seventeen times in the full structure of degraded gum. It might be mentioned here that the structures of the degraded *A. occidentale* gum and degraded *A. occidentale* shell polysaccharide⁷ differ due to slight variation in the arrangement of galactose residues in the main as well as side chain.

Experimental

Paper chromatograms were run by the descending method on Whatman No. 1 and 3 mm filter papers with the following solvent mixtures: (S₁) butan-1-ol-ethanol-water (1:1:4, upper phase), (S₂) Butan-1-ol-acetic acid-water 4:1:5, and (S₃) 2-butanone-water azeotrope⁸. Spray reagents used are (R₁) *p*-anisidine phosphate, (R₂) ethanolic solution of aniline (1%) and trichloroacetic acid (5%) and (R₃) sodium metaperiodate and benzidine B.⁹ R_g values are with reference to 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose. Evaporations were carried out at 45-50° under reduced pressure. Specific rotations are equilibrium values and the m.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectrum was taken with a Perkin Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer, model 137-B.

Degraded *A. occidentale* gum : *A. occidentale* gum (20 g) was heated with water (500 ml) on a steam bath for 90 hr when the autohydrolysis was complete (as revealed from kinetic studies). The autohydrolyzate was cooled, neutralized (barium hydroxide) and filtered. The filtrate, after concentration to 100 ml, was dialyzed against distilled water for 48 hr. The dialysed solution was made alkaline (pH 8.0) by addition of baryta solution and concentrated. The syrup on treatment with hot dry methanol furnished degraded *A. occidentale* gum as a light yellow powder. This was further

purified by refluxing with dry methanol (yield 14 g) (Found Ba, 4.93% ; Eq. Wt. 1327). The IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3333, 1602, 1370, 1143, 1075, 890 (hump) and 780 cm^{-1} . From the values of sedimentation constant (S^{20} , 1.366×10^{-13}), diffusion coefficient (D^{20} , 5.305×10^{-7}) and partial specific volume at 20° (δ , 0.63), the molecular weight of the degraded gum has been calculated to be 23250.

Hydrolysis of the degraded gum : Degraded gum (0.21g) was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (1N, 20 ml) in a sealed tube for 20 hr. The seal was broken and the hydrolyzate was worked up in the usual manner to obtain a syrup which on paper chromatographic examination (solvent S₁, spray reagent R₁) furnished only two spots corresponding to D-galactose and D-galacturonic acid. A quantitative estimation¹⁰ of the individual components showed the presence of galactose and galacturonic acid in a molar ratio of 7:1.

Methylation of the degraded gum : To a solution of the degraded gum (30 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (300 ml, 30%) was added dropwise neutral dimethyl sulphate (200 ml) during a period of 6 hr. with constant stirring and the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 10°. After allowing the reaction to continue at room temperature for 6 hr. the solution was neutralized (pH 7.0) with sulphuric acid and concentrated to half its volume when a semi-solid mass (A) floated up which was removed and kept. Crystals of sodium sulphate which separated out after cooling the concentrate was extracted with methanol. The methanolic concentrate was mixed with the aqueous filtrate and evaporated to a syrup. The combined mixture of the syrup and semi-solid mass (A) was remethylated with sodium hydroxide (100 ml) and dimethylsulphate (50 ml). The reaction product, after being worked up, was extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor at pH 8.0 for 10 hr. The aqueous layer was acidified (pH 2.0) and extracted exhaustively with chloroform. The dark red chloroform extract was concentrated to yield a partially methylated compound (20.4 g). This was further methylated twice by Purdie's method by treating with methyl iodide (80 ml) and freshly prepared silver oxide (16 g). Finally, a light yellow syrupy liquid was obtained (yield, 18.2 g ; Found : OCH₃, 41.98%). The I.R. spectrum of the compound showed absence of absorption band for -OH but contained other absorption bands at 1739, 890 and 765 cm^{-1} .

Hydrolysis of the methylated degraded gum : The methylated degraded gum (7.8 g) was hydrolysed¹¹ with cold 72% sulphuric acid (50 ml) at room temperature for 1 hr. The solution was then diluted with water to reduce the acid concentration to 12% and was heated on a steam bath for 4 hr. It was cooled, neutralized (barium carbonate) and concentrated to a thin syrup. This was made alkaline (pH 8.0), saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ethyl acetate in a liquid-liquid extractor for 10 hr to obtain the neutral methylated sugars (5.04 g). The aqueous layer, after

being acidified (pH 2.0) was extracted with ethyl acetate in the same way to obtain methylated uronic acid moiety (0.68 g). Upon paper chromatography, it gave an intense red spot (R_g 0.62 in solvent S₂, spray reagent R₂) corresponding to 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galacturonic acid. The acidic sugar was finally identified as 2:3:4-tri-O-methyl-D-galacturonic acid as reported earlier¹.

The neutral methylated sugars were found to be a mixture of four components as revealed from its paper chromatograms run in two different solvents S₁ and S₃ (Spray reagent R₁). Resolution of this mixture into its components was conducted by preparative partition chromatography on Whatman No. 3 M filter paper sheets (solvent S₁). The strips corresponding to individual methylated sugars were eluted with water and eluates were identified as follows:—

Fraction I: 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra O-methyl-D-galactose-Syrup (0.145 g, R_g 0.89 in S₁), $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 114^\circ$ (c, 1.1 in water) furnished a crystalline anilide, m.p. and m.m.p., 190°.

Fraction II: 2, 4, 6-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose-Syrup (0.303 g, R_g 0.67 in S₁), $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 92^\circ$ (c, 1.4 in water) furnished a crystalline 2,4,6-tri-O-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. and m.m.p., 177-78°.

Fraction III: 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl D-galactose-Syrup (0.298 g, R_g 0.65 in S₁), $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 142^\circ$ (c, 1.2 in water) was converted into its crystalline anilide derivative, m.p. and m.m.p., 165-66°.

Fraction IV: 2, 4-di-O-methyl-D-galactose-Syrup (0.282 g, R_g 0.40 in S₁), $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 86^\circ$ (c, 1.05 in water) crystallised from ethyl acetate in the form of needles, m.p. 103-104° (lit.¹², m.p., 103°). It gave a crystalline 2,4-di-O-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. and m.m.p. 216-17°.

A quantitative estimation of the methylated sugars by the hypiodite oxidation method¹³ showed that 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,4,6-tri-, 2,3,4-tri-, and 2,4-di-O-methyl-D-galactoses were present in a molar ratio of 1:2:2:2.

Periodate oxidation of the degraded gum: An aqueous solution of the degraded gum (0.2054 g) was treated with sodium metaperiodate solution (0.15 M, 25 ml) and the volume was made up to 250 ml with water. It was kept in the dark at room temperature for 7 days. A blank experiment was set up in the same manner with the same volume of 0.15 M sodium metaperiodate solution. Aliquots (5 ml each) were removed from both the solutions at regular intervals to determine the amount of periodate consumed and formic acid liberated.

The formic acid produced and periodate consumed at the final stage were observed to be 0.49 and 0.99 moles per anhydrohexose unit respectively.

Hydrolysis of the periodate oxidised degraded gum: An aqueous solution of the periodate oxidised degraded gum was treated with ethylene glycol to destroy excess of periodate and the inorganic ions were eliminated by dialysis. The dialysed solution was evaporated to a syrup and hydrolysed by heating with N sulphuric acid (10 ml) for 4 hr. The hydrolyzate after being worked up showed the presence of D-galactose when examined paper chromatographically. A quantitative estimation of the sugar in the hydrolyzate showed the presence of 3.89 moles of galactose per equivalent of the degraded gum.

Smith degradation of the degraded gum: The degraded gum (0.1858 g) was oxidised with sodium metaperiodate for 48 hr at room temperature until the periodate consumption became constant. Excess oxidant was removed by adding ethylene glycol and the solution was dialysed against running distilled water till it was free from inorganic ions. The dialysed polyaldehyde solution was treated with sodium borohydride (0.25 g) for 24 hours. After removal of excess borohydride by aqueous acetic acid (1:1), the solution was evaporated to dryness. The borate ions were removed as methyl borate and the borate free product was hydrolyzed with sulphuric acid (1N, 10ml) for 6 hr. The hydrolyzate, after being worked up, was evaporated to a thin syrup. This, on paper chromatographic examination (solvent S₁, reagent R₃) gave three spots corresponding to galactose, glycerol and glycolaldehyde. A part of the syrup was resolved into its components on Whatman No. 3 mm sheets. The zones corresponding to galactose and glycerol were eluted with water and individual components were estimated by phenol-sulphuric acid¹⁴ and chromotropic acid¹⁵ reagents respectively. Galactose and glycerol were found to be present in a molar ratio of 1:0.98.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Professor J. Rosik', Institute of Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Czechoslovakia for his generous help in determining the diffusion coefficient and sedimentation constant of the degraded gum and to Dr. N.A. Ramaiah, Director, for his kind interest in this investigation.

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